

THE MODULAR DISTANCE APPROACH IN TEACHING ARALING PANLIPUNAN AND LEARNING IN THE NEW NORMAL SET-UP

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the modular distance learning approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan and learning in the new normal set up. The study used descriptive research design in conducting the study. This focused on describing the modular distance learning, describing the monitoring of learners progress and evaluation of the students' academic performance. The result of the study revealed that the respondents described modular distance learning such as individualized instruction, immediate feedback, reinforcement of learning and scaffold instruction as agree. The respondents also describe the monitoring of learners progress such as home visitation and remedial teaching as Agree. Similarly the respondents described the level of their skills in terms of remembering as advanced, applying understanding and evaluating as proficient. Furthermore, there is no significant correlation between the 3 components of modular distance learning such as individualized instruction, immediate feedback, scaffold instruction and academic performance however one of the variable shows significant relationship which is reinforcement of learning to applying skills of the students. In addition the second variable which is monitoring of learners progress such as home visitation and remedial teaching show no significant relationship to academic performance.

Keywords: (a) Modular Distance Learning (b) Monitoring of learners (c) Descriptive Research; Survey Questionnaire; (d) Academic Performance